

Embracing Uncertainty in Participatory GIS: Perceptions of tree planting in the English Lake District

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Summary

One of the most significant challenges in Participatory GIS (PGIS) is ensuring that results are incorporated into decision-making processes. A key issue is the lack of a means to quantify the findings of PGIS surveys, which typically contain interdependent, contradictory and conflicting information with varying degrees of participant confidence; resulting in high levels of uncertainty that are not adequately represented in conventional methods. This research describes a novel extension to Dempster-Shafer theory that permits PGIS datasets to be quantified in a manner that adequately incorporates these uncertainties, enabling their meaningful adoption into analysis and decision-making.

KEYWORDS: Dempster Shafer, Evidence, PGIS, PPGIS, Map-Me

1 Introduction

Public Participatory GIS (PPGIS, PGIS) describes a digital, map-based system for the collection of spatial data, normally in support of decision making. However, despite a rapid increase in PGIS research over time, it remains rare that PGIS outcomes have a meaningful impact on decision-making in the ‘real world’ (Denwood et al., 2022). There are a number of key challenges that likely contribute to this issue, including issues of spatial representation (Huck et al., 2014), participant empowerment (Denwood et al., 2021), accessibility (Denwood et al., 2023), and uncertainty, which includes the extent to which PGIS data are perceived by decision makers and other official bodies as ‘reliable’. Of these issues, uncertainty is the least explored in the literature. This paper seeks to address this issue by presenting an extension of Dempster-Shafer theory that quantifies the findings of PGIS data in a manner that accounts for the associated uncertainties, facilitating informed decision making. This method is illustrated with case study on public perceptions of tree-planting in the village of Grasmere in the English Lake District.

2 Method

2.1 Data Collection

Data were collected using the Map-Me PGIS platform, which uses a ‘spray-can’ (or ‘airbrush’) -style interface in order to better reflect the inherent vagueness in participants’ spatial thoughts and feelings (Huck et al., 2019; Montello et al., 2003). Data were collected from 280 participants in response to a series of questions about landscape restoration in a facilitated setting in two popular tourist destinations. The questions included in this analysis (with number of participants who made valid responses) are:

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1. *Where, if anywhere, would you like to see more trees in the landscape?* (206 responses)
2. *Where, if anywhere, would you NOT like to see more trees in the landscape?* (145 responses)

In each case, participants were asked to accompany their map-based data with free text in response to the prompt “Please explain your mapping choices”, as well as using a slider on a scale of 1-10 to answer the question “How certain are you?”. The map interface for one of these questions is illustrated in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. The Map-Me interface for one of the questions in the survey. Data added to the map using the ‘spray can’ interface can be seen in red to the left of the map, whilst the free text box and certainty slider can be seen to the right of the screen.

2.2 Dempster Shafer Theory

Dempster-Shafer Theory (DS) is a framework for making subjective judgements based on evidence (Shafer, 1990). It is a generalisation of the Bayesian approach that differs from standard probabilistic methods in that uncertainty (or *ignorance*) is explicitly modelled alongside the evidence. The result of this is the ability to separate the notion of *belief*, which describes the extent to which the evidence *directly supports* a hypothesis; from *plausibility*, which describes the extent to which the evidence *does not refute* the hypothesis. This removes the requirement that a weak belief on one hypothesis must necessarily imply a strong belief in its negation (e.g., a lack of evidence for a location being suitable for tree planting is not interpreted as evidence that it is not suitable), which is implicit in standard probabilistic approaches (Comber et al., 2007). DS can therefore provide a more nuanced representation of the evidence than is possible using conventional methods. Based on this, a DS approach would appear well-suited to many PGIS exercises, in which evidence relating to a set of hypotheses (e.g., that a location is or is not suitable for tree planting) can be variable in level of agreement, consistency, spatial coverage and certainty.

The efficacy of DS (specifically approaches to the combination of evidence from multiple sources) has been a matter of debate both on theoretical grounds (e.g., Pearl, 1990) and due to the identification of seemingly counterintuitive results (e.g., Zadeh, 1979). New methods of combination continue to appear in the literature in order to address these concerns (e.g., Tang et al., 2023). However, combination methods tend to require that evidence sources are independent, which is not a reasonable assumption for participant opinions (Denœux, 2008). Assuming independence between participants in a PGIS dataset leads to a substantial overestimation of belief (and a corresponding underestimation of

uncertainty). Though the issue of non-independence is frequently overlooked in the applied literature, Morris (1986) described it as “*the single most important issue in practical applications [of DS]*”.

This research seeks to address this latter issue, drawing on the work of Ling and Rudd (1989) to develop a rigorous approach to the combination of non-independent spatial evidence that is suitable for use with PGIS data. Ling and Rudd (1989) demonstrate how non-independent evidence, each with differing levels of certainty, can be decomposed such that the ‘overlapping’ information can be properly accounted for in combination. Their approach is, however, limited to the specific case of only two sources of evidence (i.e., participants) and where both evidence sources comprise a simple support function (e.g., a location is either wholly suitable or wholly unsuitable for trees): neither constraint is acceptable for a typical PGIS dataset.

This research therefore extends Ling and Rudd’s method to allow for an arbitrarily large number of participants presenting either simple or separable support functions (e.g., a location may be both suitable and unsuitable for tree planting to differing degrees), each with differing levels of confidence. The method is then applied in the form of a convolution filter, whereby geographically-weighted evidence is gathered for each location in a surface covering the study area (see Huck et al., 2024; Huck et al., 2023 for examples and relevant discussion). Though the details of the method and relationship to other approaches (e.g., Dencœur, 2008) are necessarily too extensive for this short paper and results are presented below. The details of the method will be provided in an oral presentation and subsequent full-length manuscript.

3 Results

Belief and *plausibility* surfaces for locations in which participants would and would not like to see tree planting in the study area are illustrated in **Figure 2**. The broad patterns are very clear, with a preference for tree planting to take place on the valley sides, but to avoid the fell tops, lakesides and valley bottom (comprising Grasmere Village and improved grassland pasture). The extent of the uncertainty in the evidence (i.e., the difference between the belief and plausibility surface for each statement) is also clear. The collection of additional data, particularly from participants with a greater level of confidence would reduce the level of uncertainty in this analysis, and hence bring the values in the *belief* and *plausibility* surfaces closer together.

The patterns illustrated in **Figure 2** are supported by the free text responses, which are used in the decomposition of individual participants’ evidence before combination, as well as providing valuable context to the resulting patterns. For example, those relating to areas considered suitable for tree planting often refer to the expansion of additional woodland areas (which are typically located on valley sides) and the creation of ‘wildlife corridors’ between existing patches of woodland. There were also frequent references to ecosystem services such as the reduction of noise and air pollution along the roads and placement higher in the catchment to reduce flooding. Justification for the areas that were identified as not suitable for tree planting was more focused around preserving views of the lakes and fell tops. There were also concerns of accessibility, suggesting that the presence of trees might prevent access to the lakes. Avoidance of the valley appeared to be predominantly related to the desire to preserve farmland and risk to travel disruption (e.g., from trees falling onto roads). These findings are consistent with qualitative research conducted elsewhere in the region (e.g., Iversen et al., 2023).

Figure 2. Maps of Grasmere showing *belief* (top row) and *plausibility* (bottom row) surfaces representing the hypotheses that people would like (left column) and would NOT like (right column) to see tree planting in the study area.

4 Conclusion

Uncertainty is a key challenge to the meaningful incorporation of PGIS data into the decision-making process. This research contributes to the field of evidence theory by providing a flexible means to combine data from non-independent sources with differing levels of confidence in a Dempster-Shafer framework. It also advances the field of PGIS by providing a means to quantify uncertain findings from PGIS surveys in a way that can adequately account for dependence, conflict and contradiction within and between participant responses, as well as their associated level of confidence. This is a critical step towards the meaningful incorporation of such datasets into decision-making processes. The method also raises the possibility for use with other geographical datasets with high levels of uncertainty (e.g., historical writing, old maps, museum collections) into spatial analyses.

5 Acknowledgements

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6 Reproducibility Statement

All analysis was undertaken using Python 3.10. The code required to reproduce this research is available at <https://github.com/jonnyhuck/PPGIS-Uncertainty>.

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Biographies

Jonny Huck is Professor of Computational Geography at the University of Manchester. He is interested in the creation of geocomputational and participatory methods for application to a range of environmental, global health and urban applications.

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